

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE STATE OF THE NITRIC OXIDE SYSTEM IN PATIENTS WITH ECZEMA DEPENDING ON THE CLINICAL COURSE OF THE DERMATOSIS

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Abstract

The purpose of the work is to assess the state of the components of the nitric oxide system in patients with eczema, depending on the clinical course of the dermatosis.

Materials and methods. 106 eczema patients (55 men and 51 women) aged 18 to 59 were under observation. The control group was formed by 30 healthy individuals, comparable in terms of gender and age. 68 patients were diagnosed with infectious and 38 with true eczema. A widespread pathological process was identified in 83 patients, and a limited one in 23.

The acute course of dermatosis was established in 46 patients, subacute in 25, chronic in 35. The content of nitrites, nitrates, S-nitrosothiol, eNOS and mNOS activity was determined in all patients.

Results and discussion. It has been established that there is a probable increase in the content of nitrites, nitrates and S-nitrosothiol in eczema patients. The activity of eNOS decreased, and mNOS, on the contrary, increased. It has been found that the degree of depth of changes in the values of the indicators reflecting the state of the NO-system partly (the level of S-nitrosothiol, the activity of eNOS and mNOS) depends on the clinical form of eczema, the severity of inflammatory phenomena and the spread of the pathological process. The obtained data allow us to state that eczema patients have a tense state of vasotropic activity due to vasodilator regulation.

Conclusions. 1. the degree of depth of changes in the values of the indicators reflecting the state of the NO system (concentration of S-nitrosothiol, activity of eNOS and mNOS) depends in part on the clinical form of eczema, the severity of inflammatory phenomena and the spread of the pathological process.

2. in patients with eczema, there is an intensification of vasotropic activity due to the vasodilatory direction, which is combined with increased NO oxidation.

3. In patients with eczema, the levels of nitrites, nitrates, S-nitrosothiol, eNOS and mNOS activity can be taken into account as one of the additional criteria for the effectiveness of the prescribed therapy.

Keywords: Eczema, NO system, nitrites, nitrates, S-nitrosothiol, eNOS, mNOS.

Topic relevance. Eczema belongs to the group of the most widespread dermatoses. The lack of clarification of many mechanisms of development, a chronically relapsing course, frequent resistance to traditional means of therapy, a frequent tendency to the appearance of complications and deterioration of the quality of life of patients give this pathology the status of a medical and social problem [2,16]. Among the factors contributing to the manifestation of eczema are disorders of the central and peripheral nervous system, immunological state, gastrointestinal tract, peripheral blood circulation disorders, endocrine pathology, exposure to allergens, infectious agents, etc. [1, 12].

Currently, much attention is paid to the study of the role of nitric oxide (NO), as a universal transmitter, in the development of many pathological conditions. this metabolite causes the relaxation of vascular smooth muscles, takes a certain part in protection against pathogens, performs a neurotransmitter function, regulates apoptosis and cell proliferation, plays an important role in the development of secretory and reproductive mechanisms. NO formation occurs by oxidation of L-arginine by an oxygen atom in the presence of a specific enzyme, nitric oxide synthase (NOS). Depending on the structure and localization, the following isoforms

are distinguished: endothelial isoform of nitric oxide synthase (eNOS), neuronal (nNOS), and macrophage (mNOS). these isoforms differ in their mechanism of action and biosignificance for the macroorganism. Therefore, they are divided into constitutive and inducible, neuronal is only constitutive, mNOS is inducible, and eNOS is 80% constitutive and 20% inducible [10,8,20].

It has been proven that during the synthesis of NO, reactive forms of nitrogen are formed, among which S-nitrosothiol occupies a prominent place. However, it should be taken into account that in the lumen of blood vessels, NO is quickly inactivated (oxidized to nitrites and nitrates) by dissolved oxygen, superoxide anion hemoglobin. this prevents the effect of the metabolite at considerable distances from the place of its release, which makes it an important local regulator of vascular tone.

In case of disruption or impossibility of its formation (in case of endothelial dysfunction), this process is not compensated by the release of NO by intact endothelial cells of the adjacent area [22]. The main functions of NO are related to the fact that it is the most powerful of all known endogenous vasodilators.

It was established that small-caliber vessels synthesize a larger amount of this metabolite than medium and large vessels. Due to this, NO regulates peripheral resistance and the distribution of blood flow in the vascular network. Since it is responsible for vascular tone, inhibition of its synthesis or bioavailability leads to vasoconstriction [18].

The complexity of the mechanisms implementing the functional potential of NO lies in the multidirectional influence of the metabolite on the course of the pathological process. This leaves an impression on the interpretation of the obtained results, which is often debatable. Therefore, researches dedicated to the study of the NO role in the development of dermatoses have a sporadic and scattered perspective, and the obtained data are often quite contradictory. In particular, there is a report [5], that the content of NO in the blood serum of patients with psoriasis is directly correlated with the severity of the inflammatory process in the skin, and the inactive phase of the course is characterized by a low level of the metabolite. It is emphasized that NO stimulates the production of endothelial growth factor by skin epithelial cells, which promotes angiogenesis and increased keratinocyte proliferation. However, the results of another study [9], show that increased proliferation of keratinocytes occurs precisely at low concentrations of the metabolite. There is an opinion [14] that in various pathological processes there is no completely positive or negative effect of NO at its same concentration. For example, in case of allergic inflammation, its high content is able to promote eosinophilia and tissue swelling, but, on the other hand, it inhibits the release of histamine by mast cells. It has been established that as a result of oxidative stress, which is observed in allergic dermatitis, particularly in eczema and atopic dermatitis, the amount of superoxide anion increases [4,15]. Since NO is recognized as one of the most powerful antioxidants, precisely due to its ability to bind to superoxide anion, there is destruction of free metabolite, development of hypoxic state and vascular dysfunction. Endotheliopathy can lead to changes in the microcirculatory channel (a combination of blood vessel spasm with increased blood viscosity, decreased blood flow rate, defection of transcapillary blood flow), which are important in the development and course of allergic dermatitis.

In patients with atopic dermatitis, there is a decrease in the content of nitrites both in blood serum and in erythrocytes, an increase in the level of nitrates in serum and suppression of the activity of superoxide dismutase and glutathione peroxidase in heme elements. This indicates significant disorders of the oxidative pathway of L-arginine metabolism (a substrate of NO formation), weakening of antiradical protection along the enzymatic chain [21].

It has been proven that in case of allergic inflammation in the skin, IL-4 has a stimulating effect on the synthesis of NO, which increases the expression of eNOS. With a significant increase in the content of NO, peroxynitrite is formed, which leads to the development of exudation and tissue edema, i.e., accordingly, to the progression of the pathological process. Immunohistological studies of affected areas of skin in patients with

atopic dermatitis showed increased expression of eNOS in the endothelium of vessels. Clinically unchanged zone was not involved in this process. An increase in the level of NO in the endothelium of vessels of the dermis and perivascular cells leads to vasodilatation and changes in the immune response (suppression of the neutrophilic response, an increase in the content of Th2 lymphocytes). It is emphasized that the degree of skin damage in atopic dermatitis significantly correlates with the level of nitrates in blood serum [17]. The influence of the levels of metabolites of endogenous NO in patients with true eczema on the nature and severity of the course of the dermatosis has also been established [6,13,17]. However, the directionality and limits of this relationship are not defined.

Thus, the role of NO in the development of eczema remains unclear. The participation of its metabolites in the clinical course of dermatosis, the interrelationship of individual constituent factors characterizing the state of the NO system has not been investigated. The resolution of these issues will allow us to identify the priority guidelines for prescribing therapy.

Materials and methods. 106 patients with eczema (55 men and 51 women) aged 18 to 59 years were monitored. In each individual case, the diagnosis was made on the basis of a clinical examination of the patient, taking into account anamnestic data. The control group formed by 30 healthy people, comparable in terms of gender and age. 68 patients were diagnosed with infectious and 38 with true forms of eczema. In 83 patients, a stratified pathological process was identified, and limited in 23 patients. A limited acute course of dermatosis was established in 46 patients, subacute in 25 patients, chronic in 35 patients. The duration of the disease was up to 5 years in 19 patients, 5-10 years - 39 patients, 11-15 years - 25 patients and 16-20 years - 23 patients. The content of nitrites, nitrates, S-nitrosothiol, eNOS and mNOS activity in blood serum were determined in all patients.

The level of nitrates was investigated using the standard Griess reagent on a spectrophotometer "SF-46" at a wavelength of 540 nm [7]. The content of nitrates was determined using the brucine reagent [19]. The principle of the method is the ability of NOS to catalyze the transformation of L-arginine into citrulline and NO. The results were expressed in $\mu\text{mol/l}$. The activity of total NOS and mNOS was judged by the content of nitrites and nitrates. The activity of eNOS was calculated by the formula: $\text{eNOS} = \text{total NOS} - \text{mNOS}$. Results were expressed in $\text{pmol/min: mg of protein}$. The level of S-nitrosothiol was determined using the "SF-46" spectrophotometer based on the ability of NO to oxidize compounds containing SH groups [3].

Statistical processing of the research results was carried out with the help of parametric and non-parametric methods of statistical analysis generally accepted in medical and biological research on a personal computer using the programs statistica 6.0 ("StatSoft", USA) and Microsoft excel.

We determined the values of the arithmetic mean value (M), the mean square deviation (b), and the error in determining the arithmetic mean (m). The probability level of discrepancies (p) was calculated using the

student's test in the case of uneven distribution, however, the probability was determined using the non-parametric Mann-Whitney test [11].

Results and discussion. It was established that in eczema patients there is a probable increase in the content of nitrites up to $28.03 \pm 1.57 \mu\text{mol/l}$ (in the control group $-17.10 \pm 1.28 \mu\text{mol/l}$; $p < 0.05$), nitrates - up to $36.72 \pm 2.12 \mu\text{mol/l}$ (in the control group $-21.35 \pm 1.43 \mu\text{mol/l}$; $P < 0.05$), S-nitrosothiol - up to $0.47 \pm 0.04 \text{ mmol/l}$ (in the subjects of the control group $-0.28 \pm 0.03 \text{ mmol/l}$; $p < 0.05$), eNOS activity was mixed to $0.47 \pm 0.03 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ of protein (in the subjects of the control group $-0.74 \pm 0.06 \text{ pmol/min: mg}$ of protein; $p < 0.05$), and mNOS, on the contrary, increased to $0.84 \pm 0.06 \text{ pmol/min: mg}$ of protein (in subjects of the control group $-0.56 \pm 0.04 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ of protein; $p < 0.05$). It should be noted that more pronounced changes in the NO-potential are recorded in the infectious form of eczema than in the true form. In particular, pyogenic sensitization leads to an increase in the content of S-nitrosothiol to $0.54 \pm 0.02 \text{ mmol/l}$ (in true eczema $-0.40 \pm 0.03 \text{ mmol/l}$; $p < 0.05$), and mNOS activity to $0.91 \pm 0.06 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ of protein (in patients with true eczema $0.72 \pm 0.02 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ of protein; $p < 0.05$). The activity of eNOS was also probably reduced to $0.38 \pm 0.02 \text{ pmol/min: mg}$ of protein (in true eczema $-0.60 \pm 0.01 \text{ pmol/min: mg}$ of protein; $p < 0.05$). And, easier, more significant increase in the levels of nitrates - up to $29.11 \pm 1.46 \mu\text{mol/l}$ and nitrites - up to $38.15 \pm 1.96 \mu\text{mol/l}$ did not receive statistically significant confirmation (in patients with the true form of dermatosis, respectively, $26.98 \pm 1.65 \mu\text{mol/l}$, $p > 0.05$ and $34.68 \pm 2.08 \mu\text{mol/l}$; $p > 0.05$).

It was also ascertained that probably increased levels of nitrites and nitrates in eczema patients do not depend on the severity of inflammatory phenomena. In particular, the concentration of nitrites in the acute course of dermatosis is $31.15 \pm 1.39 \mu\text{mol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$), subacute $-27.96 \pm 1.60 \mu\text{mol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$), chronic $-26.88 \pm 2.31 \mu\text{mol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$). Nitrate content reaches, respectively, $37.95 \pm 1.30 \mu\text{mol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$), $36.07 \pm 1.54 \mu\text{mol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$) and $35.72 \pm 1.85 \mu\text{mol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$). The level of S-nitrosothiol in patients with subacute eczema $-0.46 \pm 0.04 \text{ mmol/l}$ is also comparable to the concentration of the metabolite in patients with acute $0.51 \pm 0.03 \text{ mmol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$) and chronic $-0.43 \pm 0.02 \text{ mmol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$) in the course of dermatosis. At the same time, acute inflammatory phenomena lead to a more significant increase in the content of S-nitrosothiol than chronic ones ($p < 0.05$). The corresponding increase in metabolite levels in subacute and chronic eczema ($p > 0.05$) also attracts attention. Suppressed activity eNOS does not depend on the severity of inflammatory phenomena and is: in the acute course of dermatosis $-0.47 \pm 0.04 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ of protein ($p > 0.05$), subacute $-0.45 \pm 0.02 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ of protein ($p > 0.05$) and chronic $-0.50 \pm 0.04 \text{ pmol/min: mg}$ of protein ($p > 0.05$). Increased activity of mNOS reaches maximum values in acute eczema $-0.92 \pm 0.05 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ protein, probably exceeding the potential of the enzyme in subacute $0.80 \pm 0.03 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ protein ($p < 0.05$) and chronic $0.71 \pm 0.02 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ of protein ($p < 0.05$). Regarding the consideration of the influence of the

spread of the pathological process, it was noted that in patients with widespread eczema, there are more significant changes in the components of the NO system. In particular, with disseminated lesions, the content of S-nitrosothiol increases to $0.56 \pm 0.04 \text{ mmol/l}$ (with limited pathological process $-0.41 \pm 0.05 \text{ mmol/l}$; $p < 0.05$), eNOS activity decreases to $0.40 \pm 0.04 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ of protein (in case of obese eczema to $0.61 \pm 0.03 \text{ pmol/min: mg}$ of protein; $p < 0.05$), and mNOS increases - up to $0.94 \pm 0.05 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ of protein (with limited eczema - up to $0.70 \pm 0.04 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ of protein; $p < 0.05$). And, only, the levels of nitrites and nitrates do not acquire features of probability: for example, if in widespread eczema they are, respectively, $29.60 \pm 1.48 \mu\text{mol/l}$ and $38.12 \pm 1.99 \mu\text{mol/l}$, then in limited - $27.09 \pm 1.55 \mu\text{mol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$) and $34.81 \pm 1.73 \mu\text{mol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$).

It has also been proven that the duration of the disease does not affect the level of nitrites and nitrates. Thus, in the interval up to 5 years, the concentration of nitrites is $29.02 \pm 1.30 \text{ pmol/l}$ (the average content in the entire contingent of patients is $-28.03 \pm 1.57 \text{ pmol/l}$; $p > 0.05$) and nitrates $-38.04 \pm 1.48 \text{ pmol/l}$ (average content in the entire contingent of patients - $36.72 \pm 2.12 \text{ pmol/l}$; $p > 0.05$), 5-10 years, respectively, $27.15 \pm 0.93 \text{ pmol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$) and $34.90 \pm 1.88 \text{ pmol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$), 11-15 years, respectively, $28.01 \pm 1.14 \text{ pmol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$) and $35.13 \pm 1.95 \text{ pmol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$), 16-20 years old, respectively, $26.98 \pm 1.52 \text{ pmol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$) and $37.16 \pm 2.08 \text{ pmol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$). A similar trend was observed in relation to the level of S-nitrosothiol and the activity of eNOS and mNOS. In particular, in the range of up to 5 years of age, the content of S-nitrosothiol was $0.44 \pm 0.03 \text{ mmol/l}$ (the average content in the entire contingent of patients - $0.47 \pm 0.04 \text{ mmol/l}$; $p > 0.05$), eNOS activity - $0.52 \pm 0.03 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ of protein (average content in the entire contingent of patients $-0.49 \pm 0.03 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ of protein; $p > 0.05$), and mNOS - $0.77 \pm 0.05 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ of protein (average content in the entire contingent of patients $-0.84 \pm 0.06 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ of protein; $p > 0.05$). With a disease duration of 5-10 years, the values of the indicators reach, respectively, $0.48 \pm 0.04 \text{ mmol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$), $0.53 \pm 0.03 \text{ pmol/min: mg}$ of protein and $0.79 \pm 0.04 \text{ pmol/min: mg}$ of protein ($p > 0.05$), 11-15 years old, respectively, $0.50 \pm 0.04 \text{ mmol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$), $0.46 \pm 0.05 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ protein ($p > 0.05$) and $0.90 \pm 0.08 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ of protein ($p > 0.05$), 16-20 years old, respectively, $0.45 \pm 0.02 \text{ mmol/l}$ ($p > 0.05$), $0.47 \pm 0.03 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ of protein ($p > 0.05$) and $0.85 \pm 0.04 \text{ pmol/min:mg}$ protein ($p > 0.05$). Thus, the degree of depth of changes in the values of indicators characterizing the state of the NO system partially depends on the clinical form of eczema, the severity of inflammatory phenomena, the prevalence of the pathological process (concentration of S-nitrosothiol, eNOS and mNOS activity), but is not consolidated with the duration of the disease. Clinical absence of elevated nitrites and nitrates content indicates a stable intensification of the NO oxidation process. However, at the same time, an increase in the level of S-nitrosothiol (a reactive form and a nitrogen donor) demonstrates an increase in the synthesis of NO. In addition, there is a redistribution of the NOS potential. An

increase in the activity of mNOS (its dominant segment) confirms the induction of the NO system. Therefore, patients with eczema have a tense state of vasotropic activity due to vasodilatory accentuation.

Conclusions.

1. the degree of depth of changes in the values of indicators reflecting the state of the NO system (concentration of S-nitrosothiol, activity of eNOS and mNOS) partly depends on the clinical form of eczema, the severity of inflammatory phenomena and the spread of the pathological process.

2. in patients with eczema, there is an intensification of vasotropic activity due to vasodilatory action, which is combined with an increase in NO oxidation.

3. in patients with eczema, the levels of nitrites, nitrates, S-nitrosothiol, eNOS and mNOS activity can be taken into account as one of the additional criteria for the effectiveness of the prescribed therapy.

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